

STRATEGIC BUSINESS MANAGEMENT THINKING

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Abstract. *In the article, the issue of achieving prospective management of each enterprise in the development of business structures is considered as a component of the management of the development strategy of our country. In this case, the need to define a strategy and act on this basis was interpreted as a trend in the formation of private business structures related to the development of market relations in the country.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, market economy, management, necessity, strategic management, planning, risk, risk.*

Introduction. It is known that in accelerating the reforms being carried out in our country, it is very important to comprehensively develop entrepreneurship in the economy. In the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan", one of the tasks focused on the development of entrepreneurship is: "integration of small business into the international community, increase and diversification of export potential, reform of the marketing system, improvement of innovative and strategic management, export of products to foreign markets, active promotion of national brands abroad. push" is [1.151]. "Rapid development of the activities of entrepreneurs is the most important guarantee of the development of our society and our prosperous life, the most important guarantee of the stable growth of our economy" [2.68]. The new stage of entrepreneurship in our country at the present time is a new, civilized stage of entrepreneurial activity in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan, which is distinguished by the process of enthusiasm, taking the example of the advanced countries of the world. Therefore, the improvement of the business environment in Uzbekistan is a clear proof of this. Therefore, it would be expedient for an entrepreneur operating in our country today to thoroughly learn the true essence of strategic management of enterprises in order to achieve the desired economic development. It helps today's entrepreneur to equip himself with the necessary theoretical and practical skills, which are the foundation of not only his own, but also social development. Analysis of literature on the topic. In our scientific research, we theoretically based on the historical decisions of the head of our state aimed at comprehensive development of entrepreneurship, defining the development strategy of our country and implementing the principles of market economy in practice [1-4].

We systematized the scientific views on the topic as follows: In the works of foreign scientists R.S.Kaplan, D.P.Norton, the main attention is focused on evaluating the main features of the strategic management system for the enterprise and organization, its effectiveness [5]. In the views of I. Ansoff, the assessment of the prospects of the enterprise and the factors affecting them in the strategic management system is studied [6]. In M. Porter's views, the place and process of innovation in the development of companies and the issues of achieving competitive advantage of companies are researched [7].

G.Sh.Khonkeldieva highlighted the solutions to management problems by evaluating the organizational-economic indicators and increasing the economic efficiency of companies[8]. R.R. Abduraupov studied the issues of improving the mechanisms of economic activity management of foreign-invested enterprises in our country [9]. In contrast to the above scientific views, B.V. Nasimov, precisely in the context of today's globalization and democratic market reforms, the issues aimed at the evaluation of the factors affecting the improvement of the efficiency of the enterprise and the development of its economic activity in the strategic management system are systematically highlighted[10]; Nodirkhanov J.N. Theoretical foundations of strategic management of small business and entrepreneurial entities [11]; Also, in the textbooks: T. Iminov, M. Butaboev, A. Kadirov, issues of management of components of business and entrepreneurial activity [12] are covered. Nevertheless, in the scientific literature, we did not find in the scientific literature the opinion that the strategic management of each business enterprise is a necessity and a component of the management of the development strategy of our country.

Research methodology. In this article, we considered the management of business enterprises in terms of historical, economic, logical principles, deterministic approach and discourse analysis method. Also, methods of scientific abstraction and systematic analysis were used in the implementation of research.

Research results. Historically, we all know that any labor activity, whether it is large or small, whether it is a manufacturing or service sector, necessarily requires more or less management. In other words, in order to ensure the development of human society, the process of continuous creation of material goods requires some level of management. Therefore, even in small groups, labor activities performed with the participation of two or more people take place through management. However, in order to control, the controller must be aware of the properties of the controlled object. In the national encyclopedia of Uzbekistan: Management (in economics) is the process of regulating and directing the state of the economic system of an economic object, it means the conscious purposeful influence of subjects, agencies on people and economic objects, which is carried out in order to direct their activities and achieve the intended results [13]. During his activity, an entrepreneur faces various situations - it is required to manage a group, a brigade, a workshop or a department, and the enterprise as a whole. Therefore, the entrepreneur-leader must be aware of the specific aspects of the industry in order to manage the labor team. These are: - structure of production, technological process; - the material and moral aspects of the use of human resources; - the continuity and efficiency of the use of financial resources; - know how to constantly ensure the management structure and its optimality; - specific necessary and organizational aspects of business activity and expected risks; - constant consideration of the fiscal policy of the country in which the business is conducted, etc.

Therefore, the goal of an entrepreneur in establishing an enterprise is profit. This is due to the wisdom of this businessman, that is, his philosophical views. Therefore, every founder who opens a new enterprise is constantly trying to make a profit, but not everyone knows how to do it. However, an enterprising person or group, armed with a new idea, differs from others in that they have a complete picture of ways to make a profit. More precisely, they know, with their long research, which sector, industry, activity or geographical region they tend to attract investment today. However, any ambitious entrepreneur aims not only to achieve the average profit rate in the market competition, but also to make more profit. Therefore, such a motive encourages the entrepreneur to achieve superiority in any competition. It certainly doesn't happen by itself. This

aspiration, the intended goal requires knowledge, experience, and high skills from the entrepreneur, and this situation creates the inner experiences, plans, and goals of the entrepreneur with the necessary perfect calculation. All this ultimately forms the entrepreneur's future plans.

In other words, the need for prospective planning in the enterprise's activities and, accordingly, the task of creating it, are opposite to the entrepreneur. Consequently, in this way, the entrepreneur has a perfect long-term planning of the expansion of his enterprise. Now that it is necessary to implement this intended long-term, profitable plan, the question naturally arises, how can this be achieved? We think that in such a situation, the necessity of strategic management of the enterprise arises, and the pursuit of a clear mechanism of its operation occurs. However, this situation requires strategic management based on the requirements of the economic laws of market relations. So what exactly is a "strategy"? As it is known, the issues related to the use of this term in circulation are discussed in er.av. 480 and 221 in the history of Ancient China, it was expressed in the work "The Art of Strategy" written by the commander Sun Tzu. The word "strategy" comes from the Greek word "strategos" - which means leadership or "the art of the general". It still means the art of planning military operations of the military commander. However, it was "priority" that allowed Alexander the Great to conquer the world. Therefore, the Strategy has brought him a worldwide reputation. Therefore, if we dwell on the original meaning, "Priority" is a deep, comprehensively developed complex, a plan, which is the realization of the main task of the enterprise and the realization of its goals. It is worth mentioning here that we do not think it is necessary to recall the different scientific approaches to defining Strategic Management in science [see p. 11.80]

Therefore, the Strategy is an embodied planning policy in the basic sense (on the way to the intended goal). From the point of view of an enterprise operating in the conditions of a market economy, as well as from a military point of view, strategy means the direction of action and the art of leading to the realization of a goal. Therefore, strategy is the time to guide the implementation of the goal. In other words, when making a decision for each process situation, it is necessary to distinguish the most important issues and directions in the development of certain actions, as well as to develop the optimal mechanism for their implementation.

Summarizing based on the above points, strategic management is the management of a business firm in such a way that it relies on human potential, focuses production activities on consumer demand, makes rapid adaptation and timely changes in the organization, and in the long term, the firm maintains its goals and the end result is to achieve the intended result. In other words, strategic management - strategic management of small business and business entities - is a set of actions that represent the measures aimed at achieving the goal of the enterprise, organization in the future.

The above considerations refer to the scale of microeconomics (enterprise) in the market economy. So, let's say that the majority of business enterprises in our country have realized strategic management and are striving for their goals. The question arises, what will happen if this strategic management process takes a national scale? Our answer to this is simple, it seems. If every target firm (enterprise) in the country understands the essence of the strategic management that we have mentioned and achieves its potential, then we will achieve a strategic management system throughout our country, on the scale of the entire society. Strategic authority in the management of the country's economy will be ensured, and ultimately, we will be able to achieve the level of development of our country that has been planned for many years. When taken

logically, such a conclusion is drawn that as each individual business firm is able to provide strategic management according to its own interests, it will become more and more compatible with the interests of the general society. Adam Smith, the great English classical economist, noticed such laws of development in his time. Even today, it is important to study the law of compatibility of interests.

Therefore, Adam Smith, in his time, showed the relationship of entrepreneurs with society. At first glance, it seems that their interest does not always coincide with the general interest of society. "Each individual seeks to use his capital in such a way that the product of which he produces is of greater value. He usually does not think of serving the benefit of society first, and he does not even realize to what extent he is enabling it. He thinks only of his own interests, works only for the sake of the name he sees, and at the same time, with the help of an invisible "hand", he also enters the path leading to a goal that does not even include his personal interests. An entrepreneur who acts only for his personal interests, often serves the interests of society more effectively than when he deliberately intends to realize this goal" [14. 392].

Thus, "...they are completely occupied with various plans and projects throughout their lives, and are distinguished by the fact that they understand more things and think better than the landed gentry" [14.391]. It is obvious that such plans and It is clearly visible that the most important actions of labor are managed, regulated and tracked in order to gain profit as a result of the innovations introduced by the projects.

"People with a lot of experience in life admit that a lot depends on management. Business management is a multifaceted, not yet fully explored, borderless science. And business is not just a way to get rich. Maybe serving the society means meeting the needs of people. Interests come together in business. Business serves to satisfy people's needs for various things, to make life beautiful and full" [12.4]. This, of course, indicates the alignment of the interests of entrepreneurs and the entire society.

So, if you take a deeper look, you can understand from the above that the main interest (motive) that indirectly motivates entrepreneurship is higher than profit. Yes, this push is a stealth strategy. In other words, the personal economic interests of the entrepreneur are always the interests of the socially known subject - workers, entrepreneurs, etc. They are always inextricably linked and harmonized with social and collective interests. Therefore, to summarize, the strategic management of business firms is the primary component of the structure of strategic management of our country. Therefore, the rational, effective strategic management of firms, companies or individual territories is directly related to the strategic management of our country, and they interact and influence each other. So it's a dialectic.

We should also remember: "When it comes to economic growth, the best strategy is to increase domestic demand" [17.94]. Although demand initially increases domestically, this ultimately leads to an increase in the country's export potential. We think that this indicates the effectiveness of reasonable strategic management.

So, what is the best management strategy in this? First of all, it is necessary for each firm, enterprise, company to create a long-term optimal-priority, alternative management mechanism based on all its capabilities. Therefore, it requires strict adherence to the principles of strategic management.

Based on the above, it can be summarized that the management philosophy of every enterprise operating in the conditions of current market competition should be formed, that is, an

ambitious entrepreneur should understand how necessary strategic management is. This means that an entrepreneur should be able to correctly understand existence in his activity. To understand the laws of economic development, it is necessary to increase knowledge based on continuous information.

"Successful managers are as rare as pearls in the sand" [17.99].

According to the conclusion of entrepreneurs with many years of experience in this regard, strategic management in enterprises should aim to study the following issues: - Creation of strategic management thinking in the management of enterprise activities; - formation, management and organization of a strategic process by an entrepreneur in his enterprise; - analysis of external and internal environment (SWOT) in enterprises and their management; - management of resources in enterprises, as well as special attention to labor resources; - a strategic approach to making management decisions in enterprises; - development and development of corporate and business strategies; - development of strategic positioning and strategic restructuring.

Studying all these issues and thoroughly implementing them requires a sufficient amount of experience and skills from the entrepreneur. Therefore, strategic management is the formation of a philosophy of a mechanism for the implementation of a separate visionary plan. In other words, the talent of separate management requires to look at private enterprises and organizations as a tool to achieve their goals in domestic and foreign markets. In this regard, among advanced foreign countries, the experience of Japan attracts our attention more.

Japan is a country that has made major innovations in the strategic management of enterprises in recent years and is a world leader in this field. The Japanese "kanban" method is the most effective in management science. Its essence is as a management system that ensures the continuous movement of production, turning raw materials into finished products and ensuring delivery to consumers. The content of this management style is: - assessment of the skills of selecting and hiring employees; - training and professional development; - setting clear goals and tasks for employees; - changing positions; - Certification is a characteristic of Japanese management. At the same time, according to the principle of training national management personnel of Japanese companies, they are used to sending future managers graduating from management universities in the country for internships at the companies' subsidiaries abroad. It is intended that the manager who graduated from the university will return to work in the same place. In Provardi, those personnel who have gained the most experience over time are distributed to the most necessary managerial positions within the country. Thanks to this tradition, staff shortages have been eliminated in Japan.

The Japanese understand management as first of all working hard and being ready to sacrifice oneself if necessary. Employees of the company are brought up in the spirit of a big family, and the interests of the company are put above all other interests. Managers and employees are always together, even at meals. Their fate is considered the same. Separation from the company seems like death.

It can be concluded that the Japanese management principles and methods can be applied to our conditions, taking into account our national traditions and values. These are the foundations for forming a new way of managing business enterprises in our country.

Accordingly, the tasks of creating a strategy are the analysis of general tasks in the industry and competition in it, analysis of the company's situation, and study of theoretical and practical knowledge about the factors that determine the company's competitive strategy.

It is clear from the above that conducting strategic management necessarily requires strategic planning. Accordingly, the task before the theoreticians is to inculcate the philosophy of strategic planning in the minds of our young entrepreneurs who are forming today.

Consequently, this in turn cannot be done without taking into account risks and dangers. Accordingly, it is necessary for today's entrepreneur to have a deep understanding of what risk is and what kind of material and moral damage it causes. However, this thought causes the entrepreneur to be the center of attention every day. It also requires a deep scientific approach to the study of this issue. At its core, risk is defined as the possibility of adverse outcomes, such as loss of profits and other causes of harm. In Russian it is called risk.

In other words, a risk is: - an action taken with the hope that the outcome will be good, assuming the possibility of danger; - the risk of complete or partial loss of resources or income; - a natural state, situation for any brave manager in the face of uncertainties; - to put it more precisely, it means the quantitative evaluation of an unfortunate outcome.

If this issue is interpreted from a spiritual point of view, it is a whole philosophy of bad luck. Yes, luck and bad luck are a dialectical unity. Therefore, businessmen are insuring the property and even the behavior of private enterprises in order not to be exposed to it. As an exception, we must not forget that there are also risks that cannot be linked to insurance. However, there is only one guarantee for all of them - if there is only one, it is the creation of a reserve fund.

In conclusion, formation of management thinking in new entrepreneurs, implementation of management strategy in small business and entrepreneurial enterprises is of great importance nowadays. The management strategy consists in aligning the capabilities of enterprises with the market situation, defining complex means of achieving the goals set to lift the population out of poverty. Therefore, in accordance with the "Strategy of Development" of the administration, the rational implementation of the chosen strategy for the development of our country on renewal and modernization plays an important role in joining our country to the ranks of advanced and developing countries in the world. This encourages our businessmen to take responsibility for their management primarily at the microeconomic level, that is, to provide employment to the population, reduce poverty, and improve their material well-being by ensuring the stable pace of socio-economic development in our country.

Conclusions and suggestions.

1. Based on the given information, it can be concluded that management in microeconomics is a component of management at the level of macroeconomics. They are inextricably linked and constantly interacting. Every businessman should know this and be able to realize that he is serving the motherland first and foremost.

2. The general result of effective management of business firms in our country ensures economic growth on a macroeconomic scale.

3. According to our scientific analysis, the Japanese "kanban" method is considered the most effective in the world practice of management science, as a management system that ensures the continuous movement of production, it is achieved by turning raw materials into finished products and ensuring delivery to consumers. Therefore, we believe that this management method is suitable for business enterprises in our country, and we recommend using it in the formation of their strategic management.

4. The widely implemented management strategy aligns the capabilities of enterprises with the situation in the domestic and foreign markets and serves as a comprehensive means of achieving the goals set to lift the population out of poverty.

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